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QSTR STUDY FOR TWO SERIES OF NOVEL SUCCINIMIDE DERIVATIVES – EVALUATION OF IN SILICO MINNOW TOXICITY

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Abstract

Fathead minnow (*Pimephales promelas*) test are applied for the evaluation of aqueous toxicity of xenobiotics. The environmental hazardous effect of newly synthesized compounds and drug candidates can also be evaluated in silico since many quantitative structure–toxicity relationship (QSTR) models are recognized as less expensive alternatives. In this study two series of succinimide derivatives were assessed for Minnow toxicity in silico by applying pkCSM online tool. Minnow toxicity was quantified as logLC50 (mM) value for all analysed compounds whereas LC50 is the concentration of a molecules necessary to cause the death of 50% of the Flathead Minnows. Physicochemical descriptors of the analysed compounds such as molar weight, molar refractivity and polar surface area were determined by the SwissADME online platform, while the lipophilicity (logD, logP) and aqueous solubility (logS) were quantified by the application of PreADMET online tool. The predicted toxicity was correlated to literature experimentally obtained lipophilicity for the observed molecules. The minnow logLC50 for all twenty-four succinimide derivatives was above -0.3 indicating very low acute toxicity. The compounds of the series C in comparison to the series D compounds had statistically significant higher minnow logLC50 ($p=0.007$) indicating lower toxic potential. The predicted toxicity was negatively correlated with molar weight ($p=1.45\times 10^{-4}$) and molar refractivity ($p=8.21\times 10^{-4}$) respectively. Minnow logLC50 values were negatively associated with both in silico (logD values on pH 7.4 and logP, respectively, $p<0.001$ for both relations), and experimentally quantified lipophilicity (R_M^0 values with acetone-water mixture, $p<0.001$ and acetonitrile-water as mobile phase $p<0.001$, respectively). Aqueous solubility was positively associated with minnow logLC50 ($p<0.001$) indicating lower toxicity for more soluble compounds. Despite the higher aquatic solubility, the compounds of the series C are recognized as less toxic molecules in comparison to the compounds of the series D.

Introduction

Fathead minnow (*Pimephales promelas*) as a small fish model is applied for risk assessment for various chemicals, xenobiotics and pollutants in the aquatic environment. Lethality test, partial and full life-cycle assays with the fathead minnow are used for the evaluation of aqueous toxicity of new chemicals and are routinely applied for regulatory programs aimed at assessing environmental risks of chemicals. Moreover, minnow is recognized as an excellent model for identification of sensitive life-stages for chemicals, predicting population-level effects and understanding the role of genomics [1,2]. Both natural compounds and synthetic drugs often contain heterocyclic core with succinimide moiety as building blocks [3]. A five-member heterocyclic lipophilic ring containing a nitrogen atom and two carbonyl groups as polar attachments is the core of the succinimides compounds [4]. Substituents with alkyl or aryl

groups attached to the carbon or nitrogen of the succinimides core increase the lipophilicity of the compounds whereas the two carbonyl groups and polar substituents contribute to increased polarity and aqueous solubility [5]. Twenty-four newly synthesized succinimide derivatives from two series (Table 1) are observed as potential drug candidates due to their antiproliferative effect. In order to fully express their potential as drugs, the compounds should be also eliminated as potential environmental hazards. Quantitative structure–toxicity relationship (QSTR) studies allow in silico prediction of toxic end-points for various xenobiotics based only on their structure and molecular descriptors [6]. The Minnow toxicity for two series of succinimide derivatives (Table 1) was evaluated in silico and their logLC50 values were associated to their structural features.

Experimental

Two series of newly synthesized succinimide derivatives (Table 1) were analysed for their Minnow toxicity through the free online software program pkCSM (<http://biosig.unimelb.edu.au/pkcsm/prediction>).

Table 1. The structures of the analyzed succinimide derivatives

Series C			Series D		
Compound	R ₁	R ₂	Compound	R ₁	R ₂
C1	-H	-H	D1	-H	-H
C2	-CH ₃	-H	D2	-OH	-H
C3	-OCH ₃	-H	D3	-OCH ₃	-H
C4	-OH	-H	D4	-COOH	-H
C5	-COOH	-H	D5	-CN	-H
C6	-H	-COCH ₃	D6	-CH ₃	-H
C7	-COCH ₃	-H	D7	-NO ₂	-H
C8	-NO ₂	-H	D8	-Cl	-H
C9	-Cl	-H	D9	-Br	-H
C10	-Br	-H	D10	-H	-Cl
C11	-I	-H	D11	-H	-Br
C12	-H	-Cl			
C13	-H	-Br			

The method is based on the lethal concentration values (LC50) measurements for 554 compounds where LC50 represents the concentration of a molecules necessary to cause the death of 50% of the Flathead Minnows. For a given compound a logLC50 is predicted and values below 0.5 mM (log LC50 < -0.3) are recognized as high acute toxicity. The Simplified Molecular-Input Line-Entry System (SMILES) specifications were generated with ChemDraw Professional (version 16.0) for all observed compounds after they were drawn as 2D and afterwards were used for further calculations. The free online platform SwissADME (<http://www.swissadme.ch/index.php>) was used to determine the molecular weight (MW),

polar surface area (PSA) and molar refractivity (MR) of the compounds analysed. The online tool PreADMET (<https://preadmet.bmdrc.kr/adme/>) was applied to determine the physicochemical descriptors including lipophilicity (logP and log D on pH=7.4) and aqueous solubility (logS, mol/L on pH 7.4). Finally, literature data on the experimentally obtained lipophilicity of the analysed compounds were used for comparison. The experimental lipophilicity was presented as retention R_M^0 values calculated by thin-layer reversed-phase chromatography when acetone-water and acetonitrile-water mixtures were applied as mobile phases respectively [7]. The statistical analysis was performed by the use of OriginPro 8.

Results and discussion

The Minnow toxicity for all twenty-four succinimide derivatives is given on Figure 1. All analysed succinimide derivatives have logLC50 which is far above -0.3 indicating very low acute minnow toxicity. The predicted Minnow toxicity LC50 were statistically significant higher for less lipophilic compounds of the series C in comparison to the series D structures ($p=0.007$, Figure 2) indicating lower toxicity for the compounds of the series C. Given the fact that the compounds of the C series are more polar and less lipophilic, their permeability through biological membranes is restricted which may be the key factor for limited toxicity in the aqueous environment. The predicted toxicity was negatively correlated with molar weight (adj. $r^2=0.465$, $p=1.45\times 10^{-4}$) and molar refractivity (adj. $r^2=0.378$, $p=8.21\times 10^{-4}$) respectively, while no statistically significant association with the polar surface area ($p=0.103$) was observed. In silico and experimentally quantified lipophilicity was negatively associated with minnow logLC50 values confirming that the more lipophilic compounds have higher toxic potential. Thus, logLC50 was statistically significant correlated to predicted logD values on pH 7.4 (adj. $r^2=0.764$, $p=1.48\times 10^{-8}$) and log P (adj. $r^2=0.762$, $p=1.60\times 10^{-8}$) respectively and also with R_M^0 values obtained with acetone-water mixture as mobile phase (adj. $r^2=0.767$, $p=1.16\times 10^{-8}$, Figure 3) and acetonitrile-water as mobile phase (adj. $r^2=0.575$, $p=1.05\times 10^{-5}$) respectively. The minnow logLC50 values for the analysed compounds had positive correlation with logS values (adj. $r^2=0.567$, $p=1.33\times 10^{-5}$) which indicates increased toxic potential for compounds with lower aqueous solubility.

Figure 1. Minnow toxicity of the analysed compounds obtained through pkCSM online tool

Figure 2. Statistically significant higher minnow LC50 values for compounds of the series C in comparison to series D molecules indicating lower toxicity

Figure 3. Correlation of Minnow toxicity of the analysed compounds with experimentally obtained lipophilicity expressed as R_M^0

Conclusion

The QSTR analysis indicated that the analysed succinimide derivatives have minnow logLC50 above -0.3 log mM values suggesting low acute minnow toxicity. The compounds of the series C despite their higher aquatic solubility are less toxic as less lipophilic molecules in comparison to the compounds of the series D.

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